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Building the optimal hybrid spatial Data-Driven Model: Balancing accuracy and complexity

Emanuele Barca^{*} , Maria Clementina Caputo, Rita Masciale

Water Research Institute, National Research Council of Italy, 70132 Bari, Italy

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ABSTRACT

Mapping environmental variables is crucial for natural resource management. Researchers and scholars have continually advanced this field with modern techniques such as Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation (INLA), Deep Learning (DL), and Graph Neural Networks (GNN) models. While effective, these models often present a significant challenge due to their *black* nature, which obscures the process of generating final maps from raw data. Recent theoretical breakthroughs have shown that white/grey-box models can achieve the same level of accuracy as these advanced techniques, debunking the belief that complex models are necessarily the most accurate. Based on these findings, we have developed a methodology that employs a series of statistical tests and data analytics to identify essential features hidden in spatial data in order to assess the predictive model (of white/grey kind) that best approximates underlying spatial processes. This methodology profiles the model that better adapts to the data, aiding in the selection of the simplest model that achieves the desired accuracy, functioning similarly to a recommender system for model selection. Furthermore, the set of permissible models includes only regressive-like ones to clarify the data's contribution to map construction and can be applied to a wide range of datasets. By reducing complexity, this approach enhances the transparency of the model's results. Real-world dataset demonstrates this methodology's remarkable ability to produce highly accurate results.

1. Introduction

Environmental variable mapping is crucial for effective natural resource management, providing essential information for decision-making processes. High predictive accuracy is vital to ensure mapping effectiveness and subsequent decision-making efficacy. While researchers continually develop new approaches within various theoretical frameworks, implemented in platforms like R or Python (Chen et al., 2021), the increased availability of machine learning (ML) models for mapping spatial observational datasets presents both advantages and challenges. In Table 1 are reported the main functions and the relative libraries used in the methodology.

The primary challenges include:

- i) The overwhelming and time-consuming process of selection from an extensive list of models.
- ii) The tendency to default to familiar models repeatedly, potentially missing opportunities for more accurate or efficient alternatives (Saez & Barceló, 2022; Prost et al., 2008; Meyer et al., 2018).

In this context, many scientific contributions focus on improving prediction accuracy (Czupryna et al., 2018), however this improved accuracy often comes at the cost of increased model complexity. Consequently, there is a widespread belief among scholars that the most accurate models are inherently the most complex. Previous efforts to reduce model complexity have primarily focused on reducing computational costs rather than increasing the clarity of relationships between response and covariates (Maddox et al., 2019). This study aims to challenge this belief by presenting a methodology grounded in the confidence that models which are more interpretable—i.e., white/grey-box models—can be as accurate as their more complex counterparts. This confidence is based on Wolpert's theorem and recent theoretical findings establishing equivalence between very complex models like deep neural networks and simpler models such as decision trees and Gaussian processes (Aytekin, 2022; Lee et al., 2017), evidencing a scientific trend aiming to demonstrate that simpler models can be effective in prediction as much as complex ones (Schmidt-Hieber, 2021). The need for tuning model selection is theoretically grounded in the “no free lunch” theorem (NFLT) for machine learning, which states that *no model*

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: emanuele.barca@ba.irsra.cnr.it (E. Barca), maria.caputo@ba.irsra.cnr.it (M.C. Caputo), rita.masciale@ba.irsra.cnr.it (R. Masciale).

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Table 1
model list with related R functions and libraries.

Model	R function	Library
Kriging	autofitVariogram	automap
LM	lm	stats
GLM	glm	stats
GAM	gam	mgcv
MARS	earth	earth
SVC (GWR)	GWRModel	GWRModel

can outperform all others across all possible datasets (Wolpert, 1996). Wolpert’s proposed an approach for model selection, popularized as *SuperLearner* that uses cross-validation to estimate the performance of multiple ML models (Polley & Van Der Laan, 2010; Breiman, 1996); however, it does not provide clear insights into the effectiveness of the best model selected. This paper presents a methodology that applies a reverse perspective compared to *SuperLearner*. Instead of applying a long list of models to the dataset, a set of statistical tests is carried out to identify key features in the data, determining the main features that the

Fig. 1. Location of the study area and selected monitoring wells. The polygon formed by the convex hull of the monitoring points is also shown.

model should have to better represent the dataset. This feature selection process ensures that the model remains interpretable while retaining predictive power. Building on this foundation, the methodology for analyzing spatial processes is based on a fundamental yet comprehensive assumption applicable to a wide range of practical situations. In geographic domains, the spatial process $Z(x)$ can be expressed as:

$$Z(x) = \mu(x) + W(x) + \varepsilon(x) \quad x \in D \quad (1)$$

where $\mu(x)$ defines the spatial trend component (large-scale variation or non-stationary process), $W(x)$ is a stationary spatially-dependent (stochastic) process representing medium/small-scale variation (Cressie, 1993), and $\varepsilon(x)$ represents the white noise, a Gaussian zero-mean spatially uncorrelated and homoscedastic component related to random measurement errors (Popolizio et al., 2022). This equation provides a general framework for analyzing spatial processes, adaptable on specific research questions and datasets. The selection of regression-based models, including GLM, GAM, MARS, GWR and Ordinary Kriging, ensures flexibility across different datasets. These models impose no distributional constraints on the data itself, but only on the model residuals. Moreover, their robustness to deviations from Gaussianity in the residuals is well established.

The validation of the proposed methodology has been carried out using a case study of recorded groundwater levels in the Apulia Region of Southern Italy, comparing its performance against traditional modeling approaches in terms of accuracy and interpretability. The validation of the methodology on a real-world case achieved an optimal result. Specifically, the root mean square error (RMSE) of the model is 2.01 m, representing the average magnitude of prediction errors. This result is particularly significant given the challenges of the case study, such as the uneven distribution of observation points, the limited number of observations, and the scarcity of available covariates. Moreover, the obtained model outperformed the benchmark used for comparison, the Co-located Co-Kriging, achieving a narrower range of error. The benchmark was selected to be consistent with the models used in this study, as all are classified as white/grey box models.

2. Study area

The proposed methodology was applied to the Alimini water system located in the southern part of Apulia Region (Salento peninsula) on the Adriatic coast (Fig. 1). The water system consists of two shallow coastal lakes, named Alimini Grande and Alimini Piccolo, and represents the southernmost residual edge of a long system of coastal wetlands (Guerricchio and Zezza, 1982). The study area, large about 50 km², is flat with a gentle slope rising toward the west side and is particularly challenging from the hydrogeological standpoint.

Geological and stratigraphical setting of the area makes possible the presence of two distinct aquifers at different depths (Margiotta and Negri, 2004; Maggiore and Pagliarulo, 2004). Particularly, the lakes are fed by the shallower unconfined multi-layer porous aquifer through a number of springs that are along their shores and represent the base level of discharge for the groundwater system. The aquifer is hosted in the Uggiano la Chiesa Formation (Pliocene) consisting of biodetritical calcarenites and yellowish calcareous sands, well stratified and very fossiliferous, medium to low permeable. In the area close to the lakes, the aquifer has a greater thickness (about 50 m) and the presence of a more cemented layer of calcarenites, outcropping in the western area of basin, implies deeper water-bearing layers. Moreover, the calcarenite rocks favor the creation of karst landforms, as dolines and sinkholes. These structures justify the presence of a discontinuous drainage network and represent preferential pathways facilitating groundwater recharge. Consequently, the extension of the hydrogeologic basin is greater than the hydrologic one (Guerricchio and Zezza, 1982; Maggiore and Pagliarulo, 2004).

The two lakes connected through a natural channel, although fed by

the same shallow groundwater system, have physical, hydrological and ecological features completely different. So, they can be considered quite distinct environments (Valdrucci et al, 2004). Alimini Grande Lake is actually a lagoon connected to the Adriatic Sea through a narrow entrance. As a consequence, it is subject to tidal level variations and characterized by brackish water particularly suitable for fish farming (Basset et al, 2001). Alimini Piccolo, instead, isolated from the open sea, is a freshwater lake. Since 1950, when a rural aqueduct was built, Alimini Piccolo has provided the surrounding area with water for agriculture and domestic use by means of intake structures. Nevertheless, numerous private dug and drilled wells exist in the area, especially in the downstream area of the lakes where tourist activities and residential areas are mainly concentrated. Overall, the groundwater resources are vital for the ecosystem, human activities and agriculture of the area, and suffer from a high degree of anthropic pressure (Griebler, C., & Avramov, M.;2015).

The hydrogeological structure of the considered groundwater system together with its overexploitation, mainly during the summer season, addressed the choice of this area to test the proposed methodology due to the superimposition of effects at different scales. Particularly, the hydrogeological setup affects the shape of the water table at the large scale, while the unplanned withdrawal from irregularly distributed wells cause changes of the water table elevation at small scale producing a source of noise in data. Moreover, the above-described features of the area lead the authors to believe that the conditions of topography-controlled water table set out by Haitjema and Mitchell-Bruker (2005) are met and justify the use of a Digital Terrain Model (DTM) as auxiliary variable. The data used to test the methodology was collected during July 2014, corresponding to the dry period that is the maximum stress for the groundwater system.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. The list of candidate models

To obtain a model that closely approximates the spatial process underlying the data (as described in EQ. (1)), it is necessary to select candidates for the two components of EQ. (1), $\mu(x)$ and $W(x)$, from a predefined set of options.

The stochastic part of EQ. (1), $W(x)$, is assigned always to the Ordinary Kriging predictor (Saez & Barcelo, 2022). This choice aligns with the declared objective of this work, which is to use only models that offer greater interpretability compared to other spatial prediction approaches. In contrast, methods such as *Graph Neural Networks* (GNN) and *Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation* (INLA) (both black-box models) exhibit higher internal complexity and lower interpretability.

The trend part, $\mu(x)$, is assigned to a model from a list that includes deterministic regressive models of increasing complexity (Li & Heap, 2011; Li et al., 2014). Combining these two models (μ and W) results in a hybrid model that incorporates both the spatial correlation captured by $W(x)$ and the spatial trend captured by $\mu(x)$. The considered model list starts from the simple linear model and progresses to more complex models capable of dealing with non-Gaussianity, non-linearities, and spatially varying relationships. The list consists of five models: Simple Linear Model (LM), Generalized Linear Model (GLM), Generalized Additive Model (GAM), Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines (MARS), and a Spatially Varying Coefficient (SVC) Model (namely, Geographically Weighted Regression – GWR) (Li & Heap, 2011; Li et al., 2014; Brunson et al., 1996). The selection policy was as follows:

LM (Linear Model) and GLM (Generalized Linear Model) → White Boxes.

They are fully interpretable, with directly readable coefficients and a clear relationship between independent (covariates) and dependent variables (response).

GAM (Generalized Additive Model) → At the boundary between White and Grey Box.

It retains an interpretable structure (thanks to the additive effects of the variables), but the use of nonlinear splines makes the interpretation less straightforward compared to a GLM. However, it is still possible to visualize and understand the effects.

MARS (Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines) → Grey Box.

Although based on local regressions, it automatically introduces partitioning (hinges), making direct interpretation of coefficients more difficult. The relationship between variables and output is less transparent.

GWR (Geographically Weighted Regression) → Grey Box.

While it is still a regression model, its coefficients vary spatially, complicating the global interpretation of the model. The local dependencies make the relationship between variables and results less clear.

The first two models are linear, with the first being parametric and the second non-parametric (LM and GLM), both lacking explicit spatial features and operating at a global scale. GAM serves as an intermediate point between linear models and fully-fledged non-linear models, incorporating some local adaptivity. MARS is a non-linear model that automatically captures complex interactions between covariates at a global level, while SVC handles locally varying characteristics of covariates. The proposed list contains only a few models with respect the superlearner, and the final equation (EQ. 1) will contain only two (or one) according to the statistical test outcomes. The Generalized Linear Model (GLM) represents the simplest form of non-parametric regression since it offers great computational speed and intuitive interpretation of its coefficients. The general (matrix) form of GLM is as follows:

$$E(X|Y) = \mu = g^{-1}(X\beta) \tag{2}$$

The LM is a simpler case of GLM in which $g^{-1} = I$, that entails $E(X|Y) = \mu = X\beta = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i x_i$.

GAM is an extension of GLM (Hastie and Tibshirani, 1990; Wood, 2017) where the predictor is not restricted to be linear in the covariates x_i s but is the sum of smoothing functions (splines) applied to the x_i s:

$$E(X|Y) = \mu = g_{-1}(b) = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p f_i(x_i) \tag{3}$$

where g is the link function that relates the response with the covariates, X is the covariate matrix, $E(X|Y)$ is the expectation of X conditional on observations Y , b is a linear predictor connecting the $f_i(\bullet)$ s, β is a vector of coefficients, β_0 is the constant term (Fasiolo et al., 2021; Wood, 2017). The MARS model is a more flexible, non-parametric extension of GAM. The main difference is that in GAM, non-linear terms are manually introduced by the user, whereas in MARS, the exact form of the nonlinearity is found automatically by the model (Friedman, 1991).

SVCs belong to a subclass of GAM, among the various SVC models available (Dormann et al., 2007), the GWR model offers the best balance between computational complexity and prediction accuracy, thus it is selected as the representative of the SVC class.

The following R packages were used for the model implementations:

3.2. Cross-validation

Cross-validation (CV) is a popular resampling procedure used to evaluate the predictive skills of machine learning models on a limited data sample. The CV procedure is well suited when data is scarce and part of the data used for model calibration is employed also in the validation stage. The procedure has a single parameter called k that refers to the number of groups (or folds) of approximately equal size that a given data sample is to be split into (Fig. 2). The black-boxed fold in figure is treated as a validation set (test data), and the method is calibrated on the remaining $k - 1$ folds. By comparing true versus predicted values, it is possible to assess some error index (such as the Root Mean Square Error – RMSE). At the end of the CV iterative process, the RMSE values obtained at each iteration can be averaged to summarize the entire process into a single value. Based on the computed indices, the user can judge the goodness of the used model. In the present paper $k = 10$ is used (Barca et al., 2017).

3.3. Methodology

The present methodology recalls the structure of a *Recommender system*, in that it offers “relevant” suggestions to practitioners for effective data modeling (Chen et al., 2021). Preliminary statistics and tests are used to extract from data a *profile*, which helps in selecting the best suited model from the above defined list (Fig. 3).

Assessing the trend or the regressive component $\mu(x)$ of EQ. (1) in the data:

First step: after a pre-processing to extract the basic statistics from the dataset, the first step consists in assessing the presence of the spatial trend by means of the *overall F-test* (The F-test of the overall significance compares a model with no predictors to the linear model specified by the user) of the first model in the list, namely the classical regression (Cook and Weisberg; 1999). If the *p-value* returned by the overall F-test is significant (i.e. *p-value* < 0.05) then $\mu(x)$ contains predictors otherwise it is an intercept-only model. If there are many candidates as explanatory variables, an *exploratory regression* looking for models that best explain the dependent variable (response) by sub-setting the covariates could be carried out (e.g. by means of the R function *regsubsets* in the *leaps* package). If the F-test is significant the first guess model is the linear one; however, there is the possibility that the spatial trend could be more

Fig. 2. Description of k-fold cross-validation.

Fig. 3. Flow-chart of the methodology.

complex than the simple linear model, to address this issue the *Ramsey's RESET test* is applied (Wooldridge, 2016). The RESET test (Regression Equation Specification Error Test) is used to check for specification errors in a regression model, such as the omission of nonlinear terms or interactions (function `resettest` of the library `lmtest`). Formally speaking, the RESET hypotheses are the following:

H0: The regression model is correctly specified. There is no need for additional nonlinear terms or interaction terms.

H1: The regression model is misspecified. Additional nonlinear or interaction terms are necessary to adequately describe the data.

Second step: If the outcome of the RESET test is not significant, the resulting spatial trend model is the one indicated by the outcome of the F-test and it cannot be furtherly improved, so the second step of the methodology can be skipped. Conversely, if the test is significant, we need to compare a set of models from the considered list (see section 3.2) to identify the most appropriate one for describing the dataset.

This comparison is performed by selecting models from the list of allowed options (GAM, MARS, GWR) and applying the Vuong test (Vuong, 1989). The Vuong test determines whether the more complex between two models provides significantly more information, thereby justifying its selection. The test is chosen because the models are not nested. However, relying solely on the significance of the Vuong test is insufficient to ensure that the selected model offers a meaningful improvement in goodness-of-fit while maintaining parsimony. Vuong test can be carried out by means of the R function `vuongtest` in the `nonnest2` package. Afterwards, the adjusted R2 of the considered models is also evaluated, and the percentage difference between pairs of models is computed. If this difference exceeds 5 %, the more complex model is selected. This approach ensures that the selected model not only fits the data well but also avoids unnecessary complexity, balancing fit and parsimony. The compared models, as already reported, are GAM, to intercept non-linearities, MARS, to capture interactions between covariates (O'Neil et al., 2020) and GWR for the case of non-stationary of the covariates' coefficients. Finally, the robustness of the selected spatial trend model is checked by splitting the dataset into a training and a test set and assessing the related accuracy metrics or using k-fold cross-validation in case of limited datasets.

Assessing the entire hybrid model ($\mu(x) + W(x)$):

Third step: After selecting the spatial trend model, it is necessary to ascertain the presence of spatial auto-correlation. This assessment is carried out on the trend residuals, which are defined as the difference between observations and spatial trend predictions at the same spatial locations ($z(x) - \mu(x)$). The auto-correlation test used is the global Moran's I test (see Section 4.2) or, equivalently, the Rao's Score Test (RS Test) (Anselin L., 2001), the Test can be carried out by means of the R function `lm.RStests` of the library `spatialreg`. If the Moran's I test is significant, indicating the presence of spatial auto-correlation, ordinary kriging can be applied to recover the spatial information contained in the residuals. The residuals are modelled via a variography stage and the robustness of the variogram model is checked via k-fold cross-validation. According to Equation (1), the results of both models (the spatial trend model and ordinary kriging) can be summed up to obtain the hybrid model predictions.

Stop criterion: As previously mentioned (recall Equation (1')), the stopping criterion is reached if the global residuals' distribution ($z(x) - \mu(x) - W(x)$)—which are the observations minus the entire hybrid model—is approximately Gaussian with a zero mean, with Breusch-Pagan test (Breusch & Pagan, 1979) and the Moran's I index both non-significant. One important remark on this respect, is that, due to unavoidable roundoff and truncation errors occurring during computation, meeting this stop criterion can be challenging. These errors typically affect the tails of the residuals' distribution, distorting the test's results. The cause of tests distortions is called *Binning effect*. When we're dealing with numerical computations, especially floating-point arithmetic, small errors can indeed cause values to shift from one bin to another when we're constructing a histogram or empirical distribution

of the residuals. This effect is more pronounced in the tails of the distribution for a few reasons:

- Fewer data points: The tails of a distribution typically contain fewer data points than the centre. This means that even a small number of points shifting bins can have a proportionally larger effect on the shape of the tail.
- Relative magnitude: In the tails, the relative difference between adjacent bins is often larger than in the centre of the distribution. A small absolute error can therefore more easily cause a shift between bins. To address this issue, only the central part of the global residuals' distribution (from the first quartile to the third quartile) should be considered and subjected to a Gaussian test or a rule of thumb on the skewness (if skewness belongs to the interval [-0.5, 0.5], the distribution can be considered approximately Gaussian) (Webster and Oliver, 2007). If this condition is not met, a revision of the selected trend model or a data transform is necessary.

4. Results

4.1. Water table elevation data analysis

4.1.1. Preliminary statistical analysis of water table elevation variable

The preliminary statistical analysis of the water table elevation variable revealed a significant departure from a normal distribution (Table 2). This deviation was confirmed by the Shapiro-Wilk normality test (Leslie et al., 1986), which indicated very significant non-normality (p -value = 2.66E-09). However, this departure from Gaussianity does not necessarily impact the accuracy of predictions, as long as the chosen model appropriately represents the data structure. In fact, in kriging and regression models, it is the normality of the residuals rather than the original data that is crucial for optimal predictions. Moreover, enforcing normality through data transformation can result in a significant deterioration in prediction accuracy, suggesting that the original distribution better preserves relevant predictive information.

Fig. 4 shows that the middle part of the distribution falls within the confidence bands of the Q-Q plot. This indicates that this part of the data follows a Gaussian distribution, as visually confirmed by the boxplot (Fig. 5) and the quantile imbalance value of -0.05 (Brunsdon et al., 2002), which is close to zero. When comparing the results of applying the linear model and kriging to both the original and Gaussian-transformed data, a loss of accuracy of about 11 % in predictions was observed. Based on these findings, the data was left untransformed.

The number of distance classes (12) was automatically estimated using a specific function in R, namely `autofitvariogram` of the package `automap`, based on the spatial distribution of the data. This choice is dataset-dependent and ensures an appropriate binning of distance intervals for variogram calculation. While the first two classes contain fewer pairs than the commonly suggested threshold of 25–50 (Myers, 1991), this guideline is not a strict requirement but rather a recommendation to ensure robust semivariogram estimation. Given the overall structure of our data, we deemed it appropriate to retain these classes, as their exclusion would have resulted in a loss of relevant short-range spatial information.

4.1.2. Correlation and spatial analysis

Results of correlation analysis between water table elevation and DTM X, Y and Z (the topographic elevation) coordinates are reported in Table 3. Particularly, a significant (linear) correlation was observed between water table elevation and the Z coordinate with a positive correlation coefficient of **0.91** consistent with Varouchakis et al. (2016) confirming the relationship between the groundwater table elevation and the Z coordinate. The scatter plots in Fig. 6 confirm the outcomes of the correlation analysis, in particular, for the Z variable. Moran's I statistics gives a hint about the predisposition of the variable of interest to be spatially auto-correlated. The Global Moran I index value was **0.87**

Table 2
Summary statistics and outcomes of the water table (WT).

N	mean	sd	median	min	max	skew	kurtosis
[count]	[m asl]	[dless*]	[dless*]				
84	9.04	9.42	6.53	0.01	41.01	1.64	2.45

*Note: dless = dimensionless.

Fig. 4. Q-Q plot of the water table [m asl].

Fig. 5. Histogram and boxplot of the water table.

Table 3
Pearson correlation coefficients for the water table elevation and corresponding significance of the test under the null hypothesis $H_0: \rho = 0$. Significant coefficients are reported in bold.

Variable	X	Y	Z	
	[m]	[m]	[m asl]	
Water table elevation [m asl]	-0.50	0.24	0.91	Correlation [dless*]
	1.4E-06	0.029	0.02E-06	p-value [dless*]

*Note: dless = dimensionless.

with a corresponding p-value $< 2.2E-16$. Local Moran indices assessed for shorter distances than the whole study area (short and medium scales), namely from 0.0 to 300 m and from 0.0 to 550 m, resulted in **0.977** and **0.961**, respectively.

Such results indicate a very strong spatial auto-correlation; therefore, it is expected that stationary components of EQ. (1) can give an effective contribution for mapping water tables. Fig. 7 confirms the clustering tendency of the considered variable; in fact, groupings of both larger and smaller (extremes) observations are evident, e.g. in the northern part of the figure.

4.1.3. Analysis of sampling points spreadness

The Voronoi partition was performed in order to characterize the

spreadness of the sampling locations over the study area. The spatial interpretation of polygon areas is the following: points with large areas are isolated, while points with small areas are clustered (see Fig. 7). Polygons' sizes for the true sampling vary from $1.0E + 4$ to $6.5E + 6$ [m²]. Therefore, to affirm objectively that the true sample distribution is irregular, it should be compared with a regular distribution gained by considering a sample with the same size. After assessing polygon sizes of the two different sample arrangements, the standard deviation has to be evaluated for both the polygon sets. If the points are regularly distributed, we expect that areas will be approximately equal (see Fig. 8 left and right parts) and, consequently, the standard deviation of the set of areas should be close to zero. The gained value is meant as the area dissimilarity index. $D_{true} = 747403.56$ [m²] and $D_{reg} = 96579.32$ [m²]; expectedly, the area dissimilarity value of the regular sampling is lesser than that of the true sampling. Afterwards, the following equation (EQ. (6))

$$D\% = (D_{true} - D_{reg}) / D_{reg} * 100$$

is applied to the standard deviation values. The departure of the true sampling from the regular one is of about the **673.88 %**. Therefore, following findings of Marchant and Lark (2007) there is a high risk of distortion in the Kriging predictions. A careful analysis of residuals is due to check bias in prediction.

The analysis of sampling points spreadness described above and performed in this study is recommended for any spatial analysis where the sampling locations are irregularly distributed over the study area. By comparing the true sampling distribution with a regular one and computing the area dissimilarity index, one can quantify the degree of irregularity and anticipate possible biases in spatial predictions. Therefore, we suggest that this assessment should be a standard preliminary step in similar spatial analyses.

4.1.4. Applying the methodology

First step: the assessment of the presence of the drift was carried out by considering the linear model relating the topographic variables to the water table, $WT X + Y + Z$, and checking its significance. The F-statistic was then run and resulted highly significant (p-value: $< 2.2E-16$) with an adjusted R-squared of about 83 %. Therefore, the drift exists and the μ component of EQ. (1) covariates resulted non-significant apart coefficient of the elevation (Z) $coefZ = 8.161e-01$ and p-value = $< 2e-16$. The Ramsey's RESET test yielded the following outcomes: RESET = 16.643, p-value = $9.559e-07$ and the B-P test BP = 13.68 and p-value = 0.0034 suggest that there is still information in the residuals of the linear model.

This outcome suggests three possible interpretations:

- The trend component requires a more complex formulation, potentially incorporating non-linear terms.
- The data may exhibit strong spatial autocorrelation not captured by the current model.
- Both the above interpretations.

Second step: the previous results of RESET and B-P tests indicate that the current model specification as simple linear may be incomplete.

By comparing the Vuong test of the three models considered so far, it resulted that all the three were significant according to address the first possibility, then we compared the adjusted R² values of some more complex models (GAM, MARS, GWR) against the linear model. The

Fig. 6. Scatterplot evidencing graphically, the relationship between water table [m asl] vs X, Y [m] and Z [m asl] coordinates, respectively.

Fig. 7. Bubble chart reporting the spatial distribution of the monitoring locations and the relative magnitude of each observation.

improvement in adjusted R^2 for the GAM showed an increase of about 11.7 % comparing the linear model to GAM, while the improvement from GAM to MARS was only about 1.86 % considered negligible. Therefore, the GAM model ($\mu = WT \quad ti(Z) + ti(Y, Z) + ti(X, Z) + ti(X, Y) -$ where ti stands for *tensor product smooth interaction terms*) was selected as spatial trend, the unique covariate found significant is the elevation Z, the other terms represent interactions between covariates. Additional model statistics: R^2 (adjusted): **0.985**; Deviance explained: **98.9 %**; GCV: **1.96**. The need to upgrade from the linear model to the GAM becomes evident when comparing the two models.

While the linear model finds significance only in the covariate Z (topographic elevation), the GAM finds that all interactions between covariates are highly significant (see Table 4). This leads to the conclusion that the relationship between water table elevation and the three topographic variables (X, Y, Z) is non-linear. This is confirmed by the significant increase in the adjusted R^2 value. Finally, the Vuong test establishes that GAM model fits better than GLM model. Outcomes of the test: $z = -8.496$, $p < 2.2e-16$. The test indicates very significantly ($p <$

$2.2e-16$) that the GAM model fits the data better than the generalized linear model. The negative z value reinforces that the average log-likelihood difference favors the GAM.

Third step: In the current step, the investigation focuses on the potential spatial auto-correlation within the GAM residuals. The Rao Score test for checking spatial dependence yielded: $RSerr = 2.56$, $p\text{-value} = 0.1096$. The Moran test return the following outcomes:

Moran I = -0.085 , $p\text{-value} = 0.8618$; according the outcomes of the two tests, it appears that the GAM residuals should not contain any spatial autocorrelation. Therefore, $W(x)$ component of EQ.(1) should be considered null.

Stop criterion: Applying the Shapiro-Wilk Gaussian test, the outcomes are the following: $W = 0.955$, $p\text{-value} = 0.0049$ that highlights the divergence of the GAM residual distribution from Gaussianity. The test on the skewness shows the value -0.45 that belongs to the interval $[-0.5, 0.5]$ indicating a sufficient degree of symmetry of GAM residual distribution. As already said at the previous step, there is no-spatial auto-correlation in GAM residuals and homoscedasticity test gives the last confirmation that the process can stop here: statistics = 0.1504 , $p\text{-value} = 0.414$. Finally, the RESET test yielded $RESET = 0.00114$, $p\text{-value} = 0.999$.

Based on these test results, you can conclude that:

- The GAM model has successfully captured the spatial and non-linear information in data.
- The residuals do not exhibit spatial autocorrelation or heteroscedasticity.
- The residuals follow an approximate Gaussian distribution and the model is correctly specified.
- The Vuong test for assessing the significant differences between non-nested models indicates that GAM fits the dataset better than the GLM.

The *profile* of the correct model to capture the information contained in the dataset is the Generalized Additive Model (GAM) with *tensor product smooth interaction terms*.

Fig. 8a. Voronoi partition for true (left) and regular sampling (right).

Fig. 8b. Histogram and boxplot of the residuals of the generalized additive model.

4.1.5. GAM validation stage

The validation stage for the GAM model was carried out by means of the k-fold validation with $k = 10$ to avoid the risk of overfitting. For each fold, values of RMSE and MAE were computed and, at the end of the process, those values were averaged.

The choice of $k = 10$ is a balance between the trade-off between bias and variance and the computational efficiency of the cross-validation process.

RMSE assumed an average of about 2.01[m] and a standard deviation of 0.85[m] while the MAE is about 1.5[m] on average with a standard deviation of 0.6[m]. The closeness to zero of the standard

deviation confirms the robustness of the defined model. In conclusion, based on the outcomes of the validation stage, it follows that GAM can be safely applied to the dataset with no risk of over-fitting.

4.1.6. GAM residuals analysis

In addition, it is well known that R-squared can be viewed as the rate of explained variance, then it can be said that GAM is close to explaining the almost totality of the variance contained in data. Finally, as emerges from Table 5 and Fig. 8, GAM's residuals are Gaussian (p-value exceeds the 0.05 threshold) while the water table, i.e. the response of GAM, originally was not (as highlighted in section 3.1). This is the expected

Table 4
Statistics for GAM.

Parametric Coefficients:			
Parametric Coefficient	Estimate	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	7.1139	16.06	< 2e-16 ***
Approximate Significance of Smooth Terms:			
Smooth Term	F		p-value
ti(Z)	53.710		< 2e-16
ti(Y, Z)	16.188		< 2e-16
ti(X, Z)	5.712		0.000148
ti(X, Y)	10.002		< 2e-16

result since GAM is a parametric model and its residuals have to follow the Gaussian distribution. Furthermore, the values of skewness and quantile imbalance, which are -0.15 and about 0.002, respectively, confirm that the distribution is symmetrical (Table 5 and Fig. 8).

4.1.7. Spatial analysis of GAM residuals

Analyzing the GAM residuals to test for their spatial auto-correlation, it was found that the global Moran’s I index was not significant (I = -0.074, p-value = 0.802). This fact indicates that GAM filtered out completely both the spatial trend and the stochastic effects. The combined plot (histogram and boxplot) confirms in its symmetry the approximate gaussianity of the GAM residuals. From Fig. 9, it is apparent that the larger errors appear located in the periphery of the study area due to some edge effect.

4.1.8. Co-located Co-Kriging tuning and results

The benchmark spatial method (Co-located Co-Kriging) was tuned on water table data and DTM data (Z – elevation – 423,735 points) to assess a multivariate model to make predictions. Co-Kriging (like other Geostatistical interpolators) differs from traditional machine learning models, but it can be viewed as a specific class of *eager learners* that exploit spatial dependencies to improve predictions (Fentie et al., 2014). The model tuning of Co-Kriging is slightly more complex than the one of Ordinary Kriging: the first step consists in modelling the secondary variable in univariate way.

Such model can be related to the primary variable (water table) due to the strong correlation assessed between the two variables (0.85). The variogram of the secondary variable (Z – elevation) was assessed (Table 6). The model then was subjected to the cross-validation process (k-fold = 10) with a correlation between observed and predicted larger than 0.85. The variogram model of Z variable main parameters are the following:.

The second step consists in adapting the secondary variable variogram model to both the variables to gain a global model. This model was then adapted to the linear co-regionalization model, because the global model has to respect some theoretical assumptions. The matrix of variograms is reported in Fig. 10 showing a good adaptation between data and the tuned model. Comparing Table 4 (GAM residuals base statistics) with Tables 7a and b (Co-located Co-Kriging residuals base statistics) emerges that i) GAM residuals are more symmetrical (see the skewness); ii) the residuals range of Co-located Co-Kriging is much larger than the one of GAM residuals ([-12.4, 15.54] vs. [-3.68, 2.64]); iii) the standard deviation of Co-Kriging residuals is larger than the one of GAM residuals indicating a larger variability.

The Co-Kriging model was subjected to a cross-validation (k-fold =

Table 5
Summary statistics of GAM residuals. [dless* = dimensionless].

N	Mean	sd	median	min	max	skew	kurtosis
[count]	[m asl]	[dless*]	[dless*]				
84	0	0.975	0.035	-3.68	2.64	-0.485	4.98

10) with a correlation between observed and predicted larger than 0.96, therefore the model can be considered satisfactory. The predictions have been mapped in Fig. 11.

4.2. Final maps discussion

The final maps resulting from the application of the two methods are shown in Fig. 10. By comparing the two maps, the first evident difference concerns the predictions of values below zero on the lakes’ boundary. Substantially, the presence of the two lakes, covering a significant percentage of the study area (2.12 km² that is 4.22 % of the study area), imposes precise constraints on the lowest value that the water table can assume in correspondence of the lakes’ boundaries. The lakes, connected to the sea, represent the base level of discharge for the groundwater system. This means that the lakes levels are in equilibrium with the sea level, conventionally equal to zero, and therefore, negative predictions of water table elevation are not physically possible. In Table 7 are reported the amount of negative predictions were obtained by the two methods.

The reason of the presence of negative valued predictions is probably related to the irregular distribution of sampling points over the study area and computational errors.

Others macroscopic differences among the two maps can be found in the areas where there are isolated monitoring points (about 30) that coincide with Voronoi polygons with areas larger than 10E + 6 [m²]. This is a real issue because predictions in those areas are affected by

Fig. 9. Bubble plot showing the spatial distribution of the GAM’s residuals.

Table 6
Variogram model parameters of Z variable.

Model	sill	range
Nugget	0.468	0.0
Gaussian	106.05	1673.0

Fitted Variogram Models - Raw Data

Fig. 10. Variogram matrix with single and cross-variograms.

Table 7a

Summary statistics of Co-located Co-Kriging residuals. [dless* = dimensionless].

N	Mean	sd	median	min	max	skew	kurtosis
[count]	[m asl]	[dless*]	[dless*]				
84	0.447	3.75	-0.007	-12.4	15.54	0.726	5.24

Table 7b

Count of predictions below zero.

Methods	Count	%
Co-located Co-Kriging	30,732	7.25 %
GAM	18,737	4.4 %

large uncertainty. Fortunately, in these areas, GAM better managed and compensated all the sources of uncertainty by predicting values of water table elevation that are more similar to the nearest monitoring points, in comparison of those of the benchmark. This result has a significant impact both from management and practical standpoint, significantly improving the assessment of available groundwater resource. The GAM final map results the best one in relation to the hydrogeological aspects also. Up to water table elevation of 4–5 m above sea level (m asl), it shows a trend which roughly trace the outline of the lakes. The water table tends sharply to zero level in correspondence with the lakes contour, by denoting an overall groundwater flow direction toward the lakes. The springs that are along the lakes shoreline, by gathering the flow in certain points, cause a higher hydraulic gradient (>1%), confirming that the whole Alimini system is fed by groundwater. Up to water table elevation of 13 m asl the slope of water table becomes gentler (hydraulic gradient < 1 %) while in the south-western part of the study area the water table exhibits steeper slope (hydraulic gradient > 1 %). The hydraulic gradient heterogeneity is due to the obstacle to groundwater flow caused by the more or less cementation degree of the calcarenite outcropping upstream of Alimini Piccolo Lake. Finally, the map is able to grasp the underground watershed between the two lakes highlighting their mutual independence in terms of groundwater flow.

5. Conclusions

The present work introduces a multi-step methodology which, by analyzing the outcomes of a set of statistical and spatial tests, is capable to select the most appropriate model from a list ordered by increasing complexity, considering the information contained in the data. Using the proposed methodology, a real-world dataset (water table data) has been positively analyzed and modelled. In particular, water table observations irregularly spread over an area of great hydrogeological complexity represented a challenging test for the proposed methodology. Following the described methodology, the Generalized Additive Model (GAM) emerged as the best-suited and most parsimonious model for the considered dataset. The GAM was validated and compared with a benchmark method, Co-located Co-Kriging, to demonstrate its efficacy.

The analysis of the results showed that the proposed method provided very accurate predictions. Moreover, unlike the benchmark method, the resulting residuals were uncorrelated and approximately Gaussian. Furthermore, the achieved accuracy was not obtained by using a large number of covariates and observations, but solely from only 84 observation samples and the information contained in the Digital Terrain Model (DTM) of the study area (X, Y, Z variables). Therefore, it can be concluded that the model provided by the methodology is both effective and parsimonious, resulting in a very detailed final map. This is a significant outcome that can aid in informed decision-making processes concerning water resource management including optimizing irrigation schedules in agriculture, improving flood risk assessments for urban planning and enhancing water distribution strategies in regions facing drought conditions. It should be highlighted that the proposed methodology fulfilled all its promises. Specifically, i) the resulting model exhibited greater accuracy compared to the benchmark, as evidenced by

Fig. 11. Final maps of water table levels obtained with the Generalized Additive Model (GAM) the Co-located Co-Kriging with the corresponding maps of uncertainty.

accuracy parameters such as RMSE values; ii) the maps outline that the uncertainty associated to the Co-Kriging predictions is larger than that of the GAM. iii) there is a larger number of Co-Kriging predictions with respect those of the GAM that are below zero, a value physically unacceptable; iv) when the methodology is applied, it substantially reduces the modelling effort by eliminating the need for other methods. In conclusion, the methodology proved to be very effective, and its application is currently being extended to other fields, such as soil science and precision agriculture.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Emanuele Barca: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original

draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Maria Clementina Caputo:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Data curation. **Rita Masciale:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Resources, Investigation, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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